
Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Activity of Ni(II)ternary complex of sulfaquinoxaline

Abeer A. Hamed^{1*}, Zeinab H. Abd El –Wahab², Abeer A. Faheim², Aida A. Salman²

¹Ministry of Industry, Trade, Small and Medium Enterprises. Industrial Control Authority. Ext. Ramses St. - 6th District – Nasr City.

²Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University (Girls branch), Youssif Abbas St., Nasr-City, Cairo, Egypt, P.O. Box 11754.

*Corresponding author email: Abeer1973@yahoo.com

Abstract A ternary complex of sulfaquinoxaline, SQ as primary ligand and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, HL as secondary ligand is prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductivity, IR, UV–vis spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis. The results reveal that sulfaquinoxaline, SQ coordinates with Ni(II) in bidentate mode through pyrazine nitrogen atom and secondary amine nitrogen atom. The supporting ligand (HL) uses its two O atoms in coordination with metal ions in bidentate mode. The complex is screened for antibacterial activity against tow gram positive bacteria as antibacterial agents.

Keywords antimicrobial activity, thermogravimetric analysis, UV–vis Spectroscopy, Ternary complexes, sulfaquinoxaline

1. Introduction

Sulfonamides have been used as synthetic antimicrobials since 1937 and are the oldest and most widely employed antimicrobial agents in veteran ary medicine because of their low cost and relatively high efficacy for treating bacterial diseases [1, 2]. Sulfonamides, a series of drugs containing the chemical structure of sulfanillic amide, are one of the most widely administered groups of antibiotics in animal husbandry as preventive and therapeutic agents for bacterial infective diseases [3]. Sulfaquinoxaline is a widely used antimicrobial agent of the sulfonamide class used in veterinary treatment to prevent coccidiosis and bacterial infections [4]. Mixed ligand complexes characterized by the sense that they are having at least two different kinds of ligands associated with the same metal ion in a complex.

The presence of more than one type of ligand in a complex increases chances of variation in properties expected for the complex [5]. The mixed ligand complexes have been used for various essential biological, chemical activities act as an active anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, antibiotic, also an active catalyst in reactions of hydrogenation and oxidation [6]. In view of these findings, in the work reported here, we synthesized novel mixed ligand complexes based on sulfaquinoxaline and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone. The synthesized complexes were characterized using different techniques; in addition, they were screened for in vitro antimicrobial activity.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Materials and physical measurements

All chemical used in the present work were of highest purity available. NiCl₂.6H₂O, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, are merck, 4-Amino-*N*-2-quinoxalanyl-benzenesulfonamide) (Known as sulfaquinoxaline, abbreviated SQ is sigma, DME, diethyl ether and silver nitrate were analytical grade chemical obtained from Merck chemical company.. All materials and solvents were used without further purification.

The elemental analyses of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were performed using a Perkin-Elmer CHN 2408 CHN elemental analyzer at Micro Analytical Center, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt. The infrared spectra of the ligands and the isolated solid complexes were recorded using KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer 437 IR spectrophotometer (400-4000 cm⁻¹) at Micro Analytical Center, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt. The ultraviolet and visible spectra were measured at room temperature in the UV-Vis range (200-800 nm) using Shimadzu 3101 PC UV-VIS-NIR made in Japan at Cairo University. The thermogravimetric analyzer TGA-50 SHIMA VZU and DTA, TA50 shimadzu, were used to record simultaneously the TGA curves, at Micro Analytical Center, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt. Magnetic susceptibilities of complexes in solid state were measured by the Gouy method at room temperature using a Johnson Matthey, Alfa product, model MKI magnetic susceptibility balance at Micro Analytical Center, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.

2.2. Preparation of metal complexes

An ethanoic solution (20 ml) of the nickel chloride salt (0.01 mol) was added dropwise to a mixture of sulfaquinoxaline (SQ) (0.01 mol) and 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (0.01 mol). The resulting mixture was stirred under reflux for 4hrs on a water bath. The isolated product washed with DMF and diethyl ether then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. These complexes are soluble in DMF and DMSO while insoluble in most organic solvents.

2.2.1. Antimicrobial activity

To evaluate the antimicrobial activity of the investigated compounds; SQ and mixed ligand complexes, a variety of bacterial and fungal species were chosen as follows: two bacterial species ie, *Staphylococcus aureus* (RCMB010010) and *Bacillus subtilis* (RCMB015(1)NRRL B-543 (Gram-positive bacteria); In addition, *Gentamycin* (4µg/mL) was used as standard antibacterial agent. Two fungi

3. Results and discussion

The prepared ternary complex of Ni(II) was found to be soluble in common organic solvents such as chloroform, DMF, DMSO and insoluble in ethanol, methanol and water.

3.1. Elemental analysis

Microanalysis data obtained for the metal complex confirmed that the complex is mononuclear complex with ligand to metal ratio 1:1:1. The elemental analysis data were found to be in good agreement with the proposed molecular formula (Table 1).

3.2. Conductivity measurements

Molar conductivity measurements of 10⁻³M concentration of the synthesized mixed ligand metal complex was 18 Ω⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹. This value confirmed the nonelectrolytic nature of the metal complex [7].

Table 1: Analytical and some physical data of the synthesized metal complexes

Metal complexes	M.Wt. Found (Calcd)	Meting point °C	Elemental analysis, Found / (Calcd.) %						Λ
			C	H	S	N	Cl	M	
[Ni(HL)(SQ)Cl ₂]. H ₂ O	585.48	230	44.65	3.92	7.77	16.01	11.68	9.02	0.10
NiC ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ SO ₄ Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	(584.09)		(45.23)	(3.80)	(5.49)	(9.59)	(12.14)	10.05)	

3.3. IR spectral studies

The main vibration frequencies of the SQ ligand in comparison with its nickel metal complex, Figure (1) showed a sharp band of O=S=O stretching vibration of sulfaquinoxaline is assigned at 1303 cm^{-1} but for Ni(II) complex is assigned at 1303 cm^{-1} range that suggesting that there is no ligand coordination with the metal ions occurs through the oxygen of sulfonyl group. The sharp band of N-H stretching vibration of secondary NH group of sulfaquinoxaline appears at 2865 cm^{-1} while for the complex appears at 2805 cm^{-1} for this large shift mean that there is metal ligand coordination occurred through nitrogen of secondary amino group. The band at 1653 cm^{-1} corresponding to stretching vibration of C=O of acetophenone while Ni(II) complex show this band at 1504 cm^{-1} so the shifting is significant so there is a metal ligand coordination through acetophenone carbonyl oxygen atom. The vibrational frequencies due to acetophenone phenolic —OH group was shifted to lower frequencies in Ni(II) complexes at 3358 cm^{-1} suggesting the involvement of O—H group in coordination [8]. The vibration of pyrazine nucleus, $\nu(\text{N}=\text{C})$ shifts to lower frequency in the complex with respect to the free ligand, which is suggestive of an interaction with the N-heterocyclic atoms [9].

Figure 1: IR spectra of: (a) SQ ligand (b) Ni(II)Complex

3.4. Electronic spectral analysis and Magnetic properties

The electronic spectral measurements of SQ ligand, showed two bands at 225 and 300 nm. The higher energy band is assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions, while the lower energy band is assigned to $n-\pi^*$ transitions of the SQ ligand.

Upon interaction of the ligand with the selected metal ion and comparison of the spectrum of the free ligand with its Ni(II) complex, the bands of the free ligand were exist in the complex spectra but were slightly shifted to blue or red regions. Also, new bands were observed in the spectra of the complex which are listed in Table (2). This change can be taken as a positive evidence of complex formation. The new band at 450 nm attributed to LMCT.

Ni(II) complex was found to be paramagnetic and its observed magnetic moments value is 2.69 BM indicating presence of two unpaired electrons[10].

Table 2: The magnetic properties and UV-Vis data (nm) for SQ and Ni(II) Complex.

Ligand / Complex	$\mu_{\text{eff}}^{(a)}$	Absorption bands (nm) / peak assignment			
		$\pi-\pi^*$	$n-\pi^*$	CTI ^(b)	d-d transitions / peak assignment
SQ	-	225	300		--
[Ni(HL)(SQ)Cl ₂].H ₂ O	3.69	230	285, 325	375	$675, {}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$

^(a) μ_{eff} is an experimental effective magnetic moment calculated

^(b) Charge transfer interaction.

3.5. Evaluation of the antimicrobial activity of synthesized ternary complex.

Antimicrobial activity of the ligands SQ and nickel ternary complex were individually tested against two gram positive bacterial strains namely *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* in comparison to Gentamycin as control drug. Generally, the ligand SQ is biologically active against antibacterial strains and its metal complex showed significantly enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activity against microbial strains in comparison to the free ligand. The results, the measured inhibition zone against the bacterial and fungal strains growth are listed in Table (3) and compared with standards as shown in Figure (2).

The experimental data revealed that:-

- The free ligand, SQ is itself significantly active against all the test bacterial strains. It was found to be ineffective towards *fungi*.
- Ni(II) complex more potent antibacterial agent than Ligand SQ.

It is obvious from the antimicrobial activity testing result that, the free ligand, SQ as well as its Ni(II) complex can inhibit the growth of tested bacteria with variable degree and showed remarkable zones of inhibition against the different organisms under investigation. More importantly, the role of metal ions in such activity are clear upon comparison of ligand, metal complexes and standard drugs under identical experimental conditions.

Table 3: Antimicrobial assay of SQ and Ni(II) complex.

Tested organism	Compounds under study		
	SQ	Ni	control
	Zones diameter showing inhibition in mm*		complete growth
Gram-positive bacteria:			Gentamycin ^(a)
Staphylococcus aureus (RCMB010010)	10	15	24
Bacillus subtilis (RCMB015(1)NRRL B-543)	18	15	26

Figure 2: Antibacterial activity of SQ and Ni(II) complex

4. Conclusion

In the present research studies, A ternary complex of Ni(II) with sulfaquinoxaline, SQ as primary ligand and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, HL as secondary ligand is prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductivity, IR, UV–vis spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis. The results reveal that sulfaquinoxaline, SQ coordinates with Ni(II) in bidentate mode through pyrazine nitrogen atom and secondary amine nitrogen atom. The supporting ligand (HL) uses its two O atoms in coordination with metal ions in bidentate mode. The general formula of the complex is $[\text{Ni}(\text{SQ})(\text{HL})\text{Cl}_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The results of antibacterial activity indicated that the complex have good antibacterial ability for the testing bacterium than that of sulfaquinoxaline, SQ.

Reference

- [1]. N. F. Tetzner, M. G. Maniero, C. Rodrigues-Silva and S. Rath, On-line solid phase extraction-ultra high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry as a powerful technique for the determination of sulfonamide residues in soils. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1452(2016) 89–97.
- [2]. H. Abd El-Wahab, M. Abd El-Fattah, H. M. Z. El-alfy, M. E. Owda, L. Lin and I. Hamdy, Synthesis and characterization of sulphonamide (Schiff base) ligand and its copper metal complex and their efficiency in polyurethane varnish as flame retardant and antimicrobial surface coating additives. *Prog. Org. Coatings* 142(2020)105577.
- [3]. L. Sun, L. Chen, X. Sun, X.D.Y. Yue, D. He, H. Xu, Q. Zeng, H. Wang and L. Ding, Analysis of sulfonamides in environmental water samples based on magnetic mixed hemimicelles solid-phase extraction coupled with HPLC–UV detection. *Chemosphere*, 77(2009)1306–1312.
- [4]. W. Qiu, M. Zheng, J. Sun, Y. Tian, M. Fang, Y. Zheng, T. Zhang and C. Zheng, Photolysis of enrofloxacin, pefloxacin and sulfaquinoxaline in aqueous solution by UV/H₂O₂, UV/Fe(II), and UV/H₂O₂/Fe(II) and the toxicity of the final reaction solutions on zebrafish embryos. *Sci. Total Environ.* 651(2019)1457–1468.
- [5]. D.S. Wankhede, N.A. Mandawat and A.H. Qureshi, Mixed ligand complexes derived from 4-(benzenazo)salicylaldehyde and 2-amino-4-nitrophenol using transition metal ions. *Curr. Chem. Pharm. Sc.* 4(2014)135–141.
- [6]. M. Bouhdada, M. EL Amane, and N. El Hamzaoui, Synthesis, spectroscopic studies, X-ray powder diffraction data and antibacterial activity of mixed transition metal complexes with sulfonate azo dye, sulfamate and caffeineligands. *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* 101(2019)32-39.
- [7]. B. Kavitha, M. Sravanthi, P. Saritha Reddy, DNA interaction, docking, molecular modelling and biological studies of *o*-Vanillin derived Schiff base metal complexes. *Mol. Structure* 1185(2019)153-167.
- [8]. H. Chen, X. Ma, Y. Lv, L. Jia, J. Xu, Y. Wang and Z. Ge, Four transition metal complexes with a semicarbazone ligand bearing pyrazine unit. *Mol. Struct.* 1109(2016)146–153.
- [9]. A. Z. El-Sonbati, M. A. Diab, M. S. El-Shehawy and M. Moqbal, Polymer complexes: XLX. Novel supramolecular coordination modes of structure and bonding in polymeric hydrazone sulphadruugs uranyl complexes. *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A* 75(2010)394–405.
- [10]. M. S. Refat, H. M. A. Killa and H. Fetoo, Spectroscopic and thermal characterization of Cu (II), Co (II), Ni (II) and Mn (II) complexes of fluorescent dye 4-N, N-dimethyl-ethanolamine-N-allyl-1, 8-naphthalimide (4DMEAN). *Mol. Struct.* 983(2010)122–132.

